

HYBRID CARBON/GLASS FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The properties of hybrid carbon/glass fibre composites have been studied. Several different specimen designs have been used and they have been tested in monotonic and cyclic tension, flexure and in impact. The crack-stopping ability of strips of grp in plates of cfrp shows how the incorporation of glass fibres into cfrp changes its mode of failure. However, this change does not result in any synergistic effect and the behaviour of the hybrid material seems to be simply a weighted sum of that of its constituents.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of combining two or more different types of fibre in a common matrix to produce a hybrid composite is ideally to obtain a material which exhibits some of the desirable characteristics of the unmixed composites and simultaneously to mitigate some of their unacceptable qualities. For example, the

inclusion of a quantity of high modulus fibres in an otherwise low modulus material might sufficiently stiffen the latter, without reducing its toughness, to permit the designer to save weight by using less material for a given purpose. Alternatively, the addition of cheap fibres could help to reduce the cost of a composite made from expensive carbon or boron fibres, again without seriously affecting its performance. Combining two fibres in a hybrid could also produce a material having useful properties not normally found in the constituent, single-fibre composites. All of these features could be advantageous in structural applications. The incorporation of bands of a low modulus composite in a plate reinforced mainly with high modulus fibres provides a mechanism of stopping or deflecting cracks at both the macroscopic and microscopic levels. Low-modulus strips judiciously arranged without a structure can help to localise in the high modulus regions any damage resulting from impact or cyclic loading conditions. On the microscopic scale crack blunting due to the juxtaposition of high and low modulus fibres probably accounts for much of the behaviour observed with intimately mixed hybrid fibre composites. In this paper we discuss some of these effects of composition and fibre distribution on the strength and impact resistance of carbon fibre/glass fibre hybrids.

MATERIALS USED IN THIS WORK

Three kinds of hybrid composite were prepared and tested and although the fibre and resin types are different in the three batches, the results can nevertheless be compared.

i) Laminated plates with separated fibres; sandwich structures

These were prepared by stacking together alternate layers of glass and carbon preimpregnated sheet and hot pressing. The type 1 surface-treated carbon fibre was commercial Ciba-Geigy material preimpregnated with their 905 epoxy resin. The E-glass fibres were supplied by IMI Engineering Composites Division in sheets preimpregnated with Shell Epikote 828. These sheets were

hot pressed at 180°C for 1 hr to give plates 1.4 mm thick from which unnotched plane samples 10 mm x 100 mm were cut. The sheets were stacked in a grp/cfrp/cfrp/grp sequence so as to form balanced sandwich structures in which the effects of induced stresses were minimised. The tensile behaviour of this material has been described earlier (1).

ii) Laminated plates with intermingled fibre tows

These plates contained intimately mixed glass and carbon fibre tows and were produced by the hand lay-up method using Ciba-Geigy 913 epoxy resin. Tows of type 1, surface-treated carbon fibre and sized E-glass were mixed as randomly as possible, coated with resin, rolled flat and oven-dried in the usual way. They were then hot pressed at 180°C to form plates 3 mm thick. These composites contained 25 vol.% of carbon fibre and 15 vol.% glass. Plane un-notched samples 100 mm x 10 mm x 3 mm were cut from the hot-pressed plates.

iii) Cylindrical rod samples with intermingled tows

This batch of samples was prepared from type 3, surface-treated carbon fibres, sized E-glass fibres, and polyester resin (BXL-SR-17449) by a modified form of the so-called 'pultrusion' technique. Bundles containing carbon and glass fibre tows in known proportions (by weight) were pulled from a bath of catalysed resin into glass manometer tubes with flared mouths. The samples were cured at room temperature for about 16 hours and were then post-cured at 100°C for 16 hours. When cool the composite rods could easily be slid from the tubes. They were of high quality with well-aligned fibres, low porosity and good surface finish. A roughly constant total weight fraction of fibre of about 65% was obtained by this method and the proportion (again by weight) of carbon fibre in the composite was varied in 20% steps from 0 to 100%.

TESTING TECHNIQUES

Ordinary mechanical properties were measured in the conventional way by tensile or flexural tests. The laminated sheets, which were of the order of 1 mm thick, could be broken in tension without resorting to the use of notched or reduced gauge-section tensile samples. This was an important consideration because the accumulation of damage during testing was monitored by acoustic emission detection methods and the presence of such geometrical features result in the emission of shear noise not associated with the tensile failure. In order to avoid grip damage aluminium tabs were glued onto the test strips, as discussed in an earlier paper (2). The laminated samples containing intermingled tows were 3 mm thick and could not be broken in tension without grip problems. These were therefore tested in 3-point bending using a span-to-depth ratio of 16 : 1. The effect of cyclic loading on this material was studied by repeated applications of tensile loads up to 80% of the estimated tensile fracture load. During tensile and flexure testing stress-wave emission patterns were recorded using the Dunegan system described in reference 2.

The impact resistance of the rod samples was determined by miniature Charpy testing of notched specimens. This is by no means an ideal method of comparing the impact behaviour of samples whose fracture modes are not the same, for as Bader and Ellis(3) point out notch sensitivity may falsely appear to change because there is a change from a predominantly brittle failure to a delaminating failure or because different notch depths have been used to force a brittle fracture. We found, however, that cutting a sharp circumferential notch which reduced the rod diameter by 1/6, and putting a fine saw-cut half way through a sample already containing such a circumferential notch gave results which were not significantly different. Furthermore, as we show later, changes in fracture mode did not induce any accompanying large changes in the measured fracture energy.

BEHAVIOUR OF LAMINATED HYBRID SANDWICH STRUCTURES

The stress-strain behaviour of composites containing fibres separated into layers is summarised in figure 1. The initial elastic modulus obeys a rule of mixtures, and the elastic behaviour in this region is an ideal mechanics summation of the response of the carbon and glass fibre components. Fracture of the carbon fibre layer, heralded by a small load drop and a burst of acoustic emission, begins at a strain slightly greater than that expected of plain carbon fibre reinforced plastic (cfrp). Because of the good bond between the laminations of different composition the cfrp core continues to contribute to the stiffness of the hybrid even when it is partially or completely fractured. The efficient load transfer between the grp and cfrp layers results in a situation similar to that when single brittle fibres break within a plastic matrix. At a critical distance from the fracture the carbon fibre layer is again able to take a full part in load bearing and multiple cracking of the carbon fibre layer occurs. The stress-strain curve and accompanying acoustic emission pattern show that the cfrp layer did indeed break many times during loading. This results in stress/strain behaviour which is not predictable simply from the characteristics of the component layers and which is due to the effect of good interlaminar bonding. The compliance of a well-bonded laminated hybrid increases very slowly with strain after the initial fracture of the carbon fibre layers whereas the compliance of poorly-bonded material increases precipitately at this point (1). A microscopic examination of the surface of fractured hybrid laminates shows clear evidence that the carbon layer has failed repeatedly normal to the fibre direction and the smallest broken sections are about 1.5 mm long.

Efficient transfer of stress between the cfrp and grp laminations afforded by the resin bond also accounts for the slight increase in breaking strain of the carbon fibre layers. The resin cross links at the curing temperature (180°C) at which point the

Figure 1

Typical load-strain curves for 1:1 carbon/glass fibre laminated hybrid showing behaviour of each component part.

Figure 2

Load-strain diagram obtained by combining cfrp and grp to form a hybrid composite showing effect of differential contraction.

carbon and glass fibres are unstressed. On cooling the two types of fibres attempt to contract differentially in proportion to their expansion coefficients and at room temperature equilibrium is achieved with the glass in tension, the carbon in compression, and the resin supporting the balancing shear stresses. The stress situation is illustrated schematically in figure 2. Since the carbon fibres are in compression when the composite is unloaded they eventually fail at strains slightly greater than is normal for cfrp. The eventual breaking strain of the hybrid is less than that of glass reinforced plastic, again because of the interlaminar bond, since the stiffening effect of the carbon prevents any large-scale extension of the glass layers from spreading beyond the debonded regions around fractures in the carbon fibre layers. As a consequence the grp layers are extended only locally to their limit, and their overall failure strain is therefore less than is expected of grp.

Crack stopping in cfrp laminates

Eisenmann and Kaminski (4) and McKinney (5) have incorporated strips of grp into boron fibre reinforced plastics and found that cracks running in this brittle material become arrested on entering the grp strips. We have prepared similar samples, consisting of plane, unidirectional cfrp sheets containing strips of grp 10 mm apart. The thickness of the specimens was varied from 0.4 to 1.2 mm and the test length was 100 mm. Fracture was deliberately initiated in the cfrp at 1 mm dia. holes drilled midway between two grp strips. Plain cfrp samples of the same size and shape failed in tension in a brittle fashion at right angles to the fibre alignment direction (6). In samples containing grp strips, however, cracks propagating in the cfrp were blunted when they reached the glass fibres and interfacial splitting between the two 'phases' resulted in crack arrest. The cracks did not enter the grp strips. This mechanism of crack stopping is not unexpected since glass fibres are far less rigid

Side and plan view of a three layer CFRP plate containing GRP strips

Figure 3

Idealized stress distribution across specimen containing wide strips

Figure 4

than either carbon or boron fibres. One disadvantage however is that the grp inserts seriously reduce the stiffness of the composite. To overcome this we have made samples in which the central core was plain cfrp and the outer laminations contained grp strips, all the fibres running in the same direction. Plane rectangular plates were prepared which consisted of three layers, each 0.35 mm thick. The core layer was plain cfrp and the outer cfrp layers contained strips of grp at regular intervals. The effect of this arrangement is the same as having hybrid cfrp/grp strips across the full sample thickness. Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of such a sample considered as part of an infinite plate. The dimensions of the samples and the number of crack-arrest strips was varied while the distance between the strips ($2w_1$) was kept constant at 10 mm, but we have also studied the effect of varying the width of the crack-arrest strips in order to determine the minimum width required to stop a running crack. A 1 mm diameter hole drilled midway between two grp strips usually acted successfully as a crack starter although fracture occasionally occurred in the cfrp at sites remote from the hole.

When these plates were loaded in the fibre direction fracture was initiated in the cfrp and ran into the grp/cfrp strips. In all cases, whether or not the cracks were arrested by the hybrid strips, the cracks in the outer layers of the plates were arrested immediately on reaching the grp. In plates in which cracks were successfully arrested stress whitening occurred around the region where the crack entered the strip suggesting localised debonding of the outer grp layer from the cfrp core. On removing the outer grp layer it was found that cracks in the central layer were arrested some distance beyond the point identified by the grp/cfrp boundary in the outer layer. Hybrid strips wider than about 4 mm acted as effective crack stoppers and the cracks were usually halted about 2.5 mm inside the strip. Strips narrower than about 3 mm were unable to act as crack arresters, and they showed larger

Idealized stress distribution across specimen containing narrow strips

Figure 5

Part of the load-time trace for a laminated sandwich beam

Figure 6

areas of debonding of the grp layer from the grp core.

The source of crack-arrest ability is probably simply the difference in failure modes of the cfrp core and the hybrid strip. We have shown (1) that this type of hybrid material fails only after extensive splitting and not in a brittle fashion. A crack entering a hybrid strip is thus blunted by intense shearing at the crack tip and is arrested after propagating a short distance in the strip. In addition the cfrp core of the hybrid strip will be slightly in compression as a result of differential thermal contraction. When the cfrp plate reaches its breaking stress that part within the hybrid strip is at a somewhat lower stress and can therefore resist fracture. If the width of the strips is reduced, the width of the zone of constant reduced stress, shown in figure 4, will also be reduced until it disappears and we are left with the stress situation shown in figure 5. There will thus be a limiting width which will just produce the minimum stress level to stop the crack. Once the crack has been arrested further straining is necessary before hybrid strip reaches its breaking strain and complete failure occurs.

INTIMATELY MIXED CFRP/GRP LAMINATES

A limiting case of the crack-arrest geometry discussed in the last section is of course a composite containing a random, intimate mixture of the carbon and glass tows instead of a laminated sandwich. Such a material should, according to our hypothesis of crack stopping, be less satisfactory because of the small cross-section of the grp components, but a counter argument would suggest that if propagation is easier in the intimate mix, crack initiation should nevertheless be inhibited. Samples prepared as described earlier behaved, again, as predicted by the rule of mixtures, as table 1 shows, and the initial tensile modulus of the 0.40 V_f composite was simply the sum of contributions from the relevant fractions of carbon and glass fibre components. Figure 6 shows the flexural load/deflexion

TABLE 1

CALCULATED AND ACTUAL PROPERTIES OF AN INTIMATELY MIXED CARBON/
GLASS FIBRE HYBRID

	Hybrid	Carbon fibre component	Glass fibre component
Fibre volume fraction	0.40	0.25	0.15
Calculated tensile modulus, GN/m ²	88	77	11
Measured tensile modulus, GN/m ²	86	-	-
Measured flexural strength, MN/m ²	176	-	-

behaviour of this material in 3-point bending at a span-to-depth ratio of 16 : 1 with a loading rate of 0.1 mm/min. There was no sign of any catastrophic change of load-carrying ability even when extensive splitting occurred during loading. The two halves of the specimen could not be completely separated after a test because of the unbroken glass fibres spanning the fracture zone.

This composite was subjected to cyclic tensile loading up to 80% of its estimated static fracture load. The acoustic emission generated during cycling may be compared with the emission patterns obtained previously from plain cfrp and grp (7). The intensity of acoustic emission generated during repeated tensile loading of cfrp gradually falls during cycling, and in samples that survive the first hundred or so cycles it ceases completely after about 1000 applications of load. This has been explained in terms of the stabilization of the internal structure of the cfrp. After the first cycle emission occurs only in the near vicinity of the previous maximum applied load. On the other hand, acoustic emission from samples of grp was found to approach saturation only when the specimens were loaded to less than 40%

Acoustic emission recorded during zero-tension cycling of an intimately mixed hybrid to different fractions of its static tensile failure stress.

Figure 7

of static fracture load. Above this level the rate of acoustic emission first slows down from an initial high rate, but subsequently increases rapidly until eventual failure by drastic longitudinal shearing. This mode of failure does not occur in cfrp samples.

Figure 7 shows the pattern of acoustic emission obtained when the hybrid composites were cyclically loaded. As in the case of cfrp, emissions after the first loading cycle occur only when the load is close to the previous maximum load, although apparently some random emissions were detected at other points in the cycle. At low loads the total acoustic emission quickly levelled off and specimens became acoustically silent within about 15 cycles. At 65% of the failure load acoustic emission had nearly ceased after 50 cycles although in this case occasional random emissions were detected even after 100 cycles. Emissions occurring during cycling up to 80% of failure load still occur only just prior to the previous maximum load and their intensity is again reduced during the first 20 cycles although in the hybrid this effect is less marked than in plain cfrp. It appears, therefore, that apart from the occurrence of random emissions at low and high loads, the hybrid behaves in much the same way as plain cfrp. The maximum strain level in the hybrid material during these cyclic tests was less than 10% of the breaking strain of plain grp so that apart from the odd, random fractures of the weaker glass fibres, the grp component was insufficiently highly stressed to give rise to acoustic emission.

IMPACT PROPERTIES OF INTIMATELY MIXED GRP/CFRP COMPOSITES

The technique used to prepare rod samples gave a total fibre volume fraction variation between 0.45 for plain grp and 0.60 for plain cfrp, but as figure 8 shows the actual compositions of the composites lie on a straight line section of the glass/carbon/resin ternary 'phase diagram'. The system can therefore be considered as a 'pseudo-binary' system. It should be borne in

Figure 8 Composition, flexural modulus, E , and impact fracture energy, γ_F , for hybrid GRP/CFRP composites. Closed symbols represent a more intimately-mixed structure.

mind when comparing the properties of different composites that their total V_f are not constant across the binary section, but it is unnecessary to normalise all results to a constant V_f of say 0.50 since the scaling factor would be linear.

After post-curing, the elastic modulus of 25 cm long composite rods was determined in bending before the samples were cut to 5 cm long miniature Charpy samples. The results, shown in figure 8, follow closely the expected mixture rule between plain grp and plain cfrp, and the material is apparently behaving as a well-bonded composite beam in the engineering mechanics sense. The Charpy results, also recorded in figure 8 as a function of composition, are the mean values of five or six separate determinations and they too show a linear variation between grp and cfrp. There are no unexpected 'synergistic' effects such as have been hoped for, and the results are not unlike those of Hancox and Wells (8) for Izod impact energies of sandwich beams. The open symbols in this figure represent composites in which the tows are randomly mixed, but the closed symbols represent one composition for which the tows were split up and intermingled on a more intimate scale. There is clearly no significant difference between the behaviour of the two materials but we suppose that a proper examination of intimacy of mixing would call for juxtaposition of the glass and carbon at the fibre level. It is often proposed that the total stored elastic energy in the composite (or, more precisely, in the fibres) at failure represents the main contribution to the composite impact energy. This is not so, however, in the case of these hybrids. The ratio of impact energy to stored elastic energy is proportional to $\gamma_F E_C / \sigma_C^2$, and this function, normalised to total $V_f = 0.50$, can be calculated from the data in figure 8 together with measured values of the fibre tow strengths. Its value increases by a factor of 7 from plain cfrp to plain grp, showing that the linear variation in γ_F is not simply a result of the corresponding linear increases in composite strength and stiffness as cfrp is added to grp.

CONCLUSION

The behaviour of cfrp/grp hybrids appears, for the most part, to be predictable on the basis of simple structural mechanics and a knowledge of the mechanical properties of the constituent composites.

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